

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B292
Date: 04 May 2007
Take Off: 14:59:42
Landing: 20:37:34
Flight Time: 5h37m42

Campaign: IASI – METOP and AQUA overpass

Operating Area: Oklahoma ARM site

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Steve Ball	Directflight
3	CCM	Sue Angold	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Stuart Newman	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Jamie Trembath	FAAM
6	Cloud Physics	Paul James	FAAM
7	AVAPS / CCM2	Doug Anderson	FAAM
8	ARIES	Joss Kent	Met Office
9	MARSS / Wet Neph / PSAP	Dave Pollard	Met Office
10	AMS	Will Morgan	University of Manchester
11	CVI / FWVS / SHIMS	Jeff Brown	Met Office
12	Mission Scientist 2	Alessio Bozzo	University of Bologna
14	Neph / PSAP	Dave Tiddeman	Met Office
15			
16			
17			
18			
19			
20			

Flight Track:

B292 Track 04-MAY-07

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B292
 Date: 4 May 2007
 Project: IASI
 Location: Gulf of Mexico

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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135349		Start-Up	0.09 kft	178	29'36.23N 95'10.06W
145444		ASP	0.08 kft	091	open
145952		T/O	0.06 kft	179	
151942	152452	Run 1	24.0 kft	152	
152544	153440	Run 1.2	24.0 kft	097	
152704		Video	24.0 kft	094	started
153440	153746	Profile 1	24.0 - 26.0 kft	095	
153751	154147	Run 2.1	26.1 - 26.0 kft	092	
154254	161148	Run 2.2	26.0 kft	183	Sonde 1
154454		Sonde 2	26.0 kft	187	
154654		Sonde 3	26.0 kft	185	
154853		Sonde 4	26.0 kft	185	
155427		Sonde 5	26.0 kft	182	
160126		Sonde 6	26.0 kft	184	
161411	164305	Run 3.1	27.0 kft	000	
161744		note	27.0 kft	359	Point South
162241		Sonde 7	27.0 kft	357	
162831		Sonde 8	27.0 kft	357	
164324		Video	27.0 kft	019	UFC to FFC
164627	165433	Run 3.2	27.0 kft	193	intercomparison run
165522	171747	Run 4	26.0 kft	183	
165628		Video	26.0 kft	182	Tapes Changed
165932		Sonde 9	26.1 kft	182	
171230		note	26.1 kft	183	Point South
172018	173219	Run 5	27.0 kft	011	
172555		note	27.0 kft	356	Poitrn South
172702		note	27.0 kft	357	overfly WB-57F
173308	175228	Run 6	26.0 kft	357	
173928		Sonde 10	26.0 kft	356	
175642	180739	Run 7	27.0 kft	159	overfly WB-57F
180021		note	27.0 kft	181	overfly WB-57F
180740	182216	Profile 2	27.0 - 8.1 kft	183	1300ft/min
182410	183205	Profile 2	8.1 - 0.07 kft	351	
182808		Video	3.6 kft	002	Tapes changed
183205	183213	Profile 3	0.07 - 0.11 kft	008	
183213	185840	Run 8	0.13 - 0.14 kft	000	
190122	192241	Profile 4	0.27 - 24.0 kft	180	
192242	192540	run 9	24.0 kft	188	
192717	194746	Run 10	24.1 - 24.0 kft	345	
192800		Sonde 11	24.0 kft	350	
193100		Sonde 12	24.0 kft	352	
193359		Sonde 13	24.0 kft	356	
193601		Sonde 14	24.0 kft	356	
194000		Sonde 15	24.0 kft	357	
194500		Sonde 16	24.0 kft	356	
194922	200844	Run 11	24.0 kft	298	
203734		Land	0.11 kft	178	
203914		ASP	0.12 kft	266	closed
204208		Shutdown	0.12 kft	180	29'36.23N 95'10.06W

B292 Track 04-MAY-07

**Sortie Brief Gulf of Mexico
Plus Houston plume**

Flight B292

Fri 4th May 2007

Mission Scientist: Stuart Newman

Briefing: 0800L 1300Z

Take off: 1000L 1500Z

landing: approximately 1530L

Satellite overpasses 15:46Z & 19:38Z

Aim: To underfly IASI on the MetOp satellite and AIRS on AQUA, in the Gulf of Mexico just off the sub satellite tracks, and perform intercomparison of aircraft radiometers.

Location: Gulf of Mexico.

Weather conditions: Clear skies or broken clouds.

Key instruments: ARIES, SWS, MARSS, AVAPS, Core Chem, Cloud Phys

Fixed Points: BAe 146 to follow fixed ground positions as follows:

Fixed point A (North): (27° 35' N, 92° 00' W)

Fixed point B (South): (25° 15' N, 92° 00' W)

1. Take off from Houston and transit to point A at FL260 (40 mins)
2. 2 SLRs from A to B to A at FL260. MetOp overpass 1546Z. Drop sondes (see below) (55 mins)
3. 2 SLRs for aircraft inter-comparison from A to B to A at FL260. Drop sondes. (55 mins)
4. Profile descent from A towards B to 100ft (25 mins)
5. Short SLR run to B at 100ft (10 mins)
6. SLR from B to A at 100ft (40 mins)
7. Profile ascent to FL300 from A to B & short run (35 mins)
8. SLR from B to A at FL300. AQUA overpass 1938Z. Drop sondes. (30 mins)
9. Transit to Ellington (40 mins). Total 330mins.
10. REFUEL for B293

Special notes for dropsonde launches:

2. Satellite overpass 1546Z

	<i>Time (Z)</i>	<i>Time relative to overpass (mins)</i>
#1	1536	T-10 (or at start of run)
#2	1539	T-7 (or start of run + 2mins)
#3	1542	T-4 (or start of run + 4 mins)
#4	1544	T-2 (or start of run + 6mins)

Plus 4 more sondes at separated intervals

3. Intercomparison

2 sondes (1 sonde for each inter-comparison run)

8. Satellite overpass 1938Z

2 sondes at start of run at separated intervals

plus

#13	1928	T-10
#14	1931	T-7
#15	1934	T-4
#16	1936	T-2

**Sortie Brief Gulf of Mexico
Plus Houston plume**

Flight B293

Fri 4th May 2007

Mission Scientist: Ruth Purvis

Approx Take off after refuel: 1630L 2130Z

landing: approximately 1830L 2330Z

Aim: To measure aerosol physics and chemistry in the outflow from Houston and its evolution with time. The sortie is similar to those conducted during AMPEP/VISURB, to measure the entire plume leaving the Houston city area and ideally to observe the transformation of the plume downwind of the source region.

Location: Immediately upwind of Houston and downwind of the urban area. BAe 146 will follow fixed points as defined below.

Weather conditions: Extensive boundary layer cloud is not desirable; mid and upper level cloud is not detrimental.

Key instruments: AMS, CO, O₃, PSAP, PCASP, nephelometer (ideally wet neph), CO₂ tuneable diode, CPC. **AMS requires 4 hours pump down time and 1-2 hours post flight.**

1. Take off, profile descent in downwind area to min safe alt (2200ft) for downwind leg (20mins)
2. 2 reciprocal SLRs at MSA downwind of Houston (North side) (45 mins)
3. Profile ascent to FL120 and position upwind (20 mins)
4. Profile descent to 50ft over sea upwind of Houston (South) (15mins)
5. SLR at a level in boundary layer (20 mins)
6. Profile ascent to FL100 (10 mins)
7. Transit to Ellington (20 mins) Total 150 mins

Mission scientist's debrief for JAIVEx flight B292 on 4 May 2007

S. M. Newman

Summary:

Satellite validation case complicated by variable cloud amounts.

Good coincidence of MetOp and Aqua overpasses over the ocean.

Valuable intercomparison of interferometers on FAAM 146 and NASA WB-57.

This was the final flight of the JAIVEx campaign, intended to intercept MetOp and Aqua overpasses over the Gulf of Mexico and perform a radiometer intercomparison with WB-57. The science commenced with a run at FL240, with broken Sc below clearly visible but dry above. The low level cloud was patchy, with wave-like structure forming Cu streets (corroborated by SWS and ARIES). Runs at FL260 coincided with the MetOp overpass at 1546 UTC and six sondes were dropped at this altitude.

An ascent to FL270 was made to prepare for the intercomparison with the WB-57. Due to air traffic concerns a large separation between the two aircraft had to be guaranteed before the two aircraft could match altitudes. The cloud conditions below continued to be dominated by CuSc with some clear patches in between. Two more sondes were released for the intercomparison exercise before descent to FL260 when sufficiently separated from the WB-57 on the same heading (south). A ninth sonde was dropped over now much clearer conditions below. This intercomparison run was repeated heading north, with one more sonde released and clear conditions below at times.

The FAAM 146 profiled down to 50 feet before commencing a run at 100 feet, encountering quite thick Sc between 800-2000 feet on the descent at the southern end of the area. During the run north the skies above cleared quickly, with very good clear conditions encountered. The sea surface temperature was seen to decrease steadily during the run. An ascent was then made to FL240 for the Aqua overpass at 1938 UTC. For these last high level runs there were clear sky slots interspersed with some low level cloud. A further six sondes were released to complete the science.

The presence of variable cloud amounts during this flight will complicate the analysis, but the combination of two satellite overpasses with an intercomparison of the FAAM 146 and WB-57 interferometers should make this a worthwhile exercise.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

MISSION SCIENTIST: STUART NEWMAN JAIVEX GULF INTER-COMPARISON

Flight No **B.292**
FAAM © 2004

Date **4/5/07**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1500	TAKE-OFF				Nose gear slow to retract on T/O
1504	Transit	5700'			Cloud tops \approx 5700' - 6500' Sc A few Cu towering to FL100
1515	Transit	FL213	150	$28^{\circ}30'94.18''$ N W	Temp shows v. moist below 750 m then v. dry above on ascent out of Houston
151942	R1.1	FL240	152	$28^{\circ}12'94.6''$	Prelim. run direct to starting point
152452	interr-upt	FL40			
152544	recom-mence	R1.2.1	097	$27^{\circ}42'93.42''$	Patchy low level cloud, looks clear above MARSS reports overheating on ground, concern over some data
152830	(R1.2)	FL240	096	$27^{\circ}42'93.24''$	Extensive Sc to starboard, and ahead ARCS see structure assoc. Sc
1533	"	"	095	$27^{\circ}36'92.54''$	Over Sc at low level, clear above it
153440	End R1.2	FL240	095	$27^{\circ}36'92.42''$	Sc breaking below, clearer slot
	Start P				MARSS reports moist below, dry above
153751	End P1 start R2.1	FL260	092	$27^{\circ}36'92.24''$	Prelim run to point A (North) Klimann overreading 1.2°C at FL260
154119	(R2.1)	FL260	096	$27^{\circ}36'92.0''$	Wave-like Cu patterns below, clear slots
154254	R2.2	FL260	188	$27^{\circ}24'91.54''$	dropsonde #1 154254 Quite clear below at this northern end of run, Sc field ahead
					#2 154454 T-28°C Td -48°C
					#3 154654 Wind 12ms ⁻¹ /274°
					#4 154853
154948					Wave pattern to clouds below
155030					SWS picks up cloud below
					#5 155427

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No B.292
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 Date 4/5/07

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
155515	R2.2	FL260	183	26°24'92°0'	Still Sc below, clearer patches in between
1559	"	"	"	26° 92° 0'	Gradual decrease in dew pt
					#6 160126
1603				25°36' 92°0'	Still streaks of Cu below, clear slots between
1607				25°12' 92°0'	ARIES, SWS seeing cloud below
161148	end R2.2	↗ ascent		24°48' 92°0'	Ascend to FL270 for run north in turn
161411	R3.1	FL270	356	24°54' 91°54'	Continuing streaks of Cu below clear above
161730		"	359	25°12' 91°54'	at SOUTH point
					#7 162241 CuSc below
1627		FL270	357	26°6' 91°54'	T = -30°C Td = -50°C wind 10ms ⁻¹ /326°
					#8 162831 Clearances below
1635		FL270	357	26°42' 91°54'	Passing over more "sausage like" - S. Ball clouds below
1641		"	"	27°9' 91°54'	Cloud streaks still passing below T = -30.8°C Td = -49.8°C wind 12ms ⁻¹ /318°
164305	end R3.1	"		27°30' 91°54'	Upward → forward cameras for intercomp'n
164626	R3.2	"	194	27°30' 91°54'	At FL270 & FL260 when S E mins ahead of WB-57 for intercomparison Maintaining Mach 0.55 or greater to keep ahead + pull away from WB-57
1653		FL270	183	26°54' 92°0'	More clear patches below here
165433	end R3.2	FL270 ↘ FL260	184	26°42' 92°0'	80 mile separation 1466 → WB-57 (?)
165522	R4	FL260	182	26°42' 92°0'	Quite clear below by visual, still patchy sc dropsande #9 165932
1700	"	"	183	26°12' 92°0'	Pretty clear below at the moment
1705	"	"	182	25°54' 92°0'	Patchy CuSc below
1708	"	"	183	25°36' 92°0'	Clear below to s'board, Cu streaks to port
171230			183	25°12' 92°W	At pt SOUTH now
171640		FL60	173	24°48' 91°54'	Clear below s'board

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.292**
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 Date **4/5/07**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
171747	R4 ^{end}	F2260		24°42' 91°54'	Having run south at F2260, climbing to F2270 and turning for reciprocal
172018	R5	F2270	008	24°48' 92°0'	Patchy CuSc below
172700					WB-57 passes underneath <u>just</u> part of our track heading south as we head north
173219	end R5	F270 ↓ F2260			
173308	R6	F2260	357	25°54' 91°54'	Looks quite clear below 1734
					dropsande #10 173928
175228	end R6	F2260	341	27°30' 91°54'	Extensive CuSc wave-like patterns below
175457		F2265 (climbing)			1809 - estimate for WB-57 to finish run
175642	Start R7	F2270	165	27°12' 92°0'	Heading south 1000 ft above Warner Bros.
180019					WB-57 past passes below just to our left
180213		F2270	183	26°48' 92°0'	Looks clear below
180739	end R7 start P2	F2270 ↓	183	26°18' 92°0'	Descent at 1300 ft/min because we were delayed by air traffic before descent
1816	(P2)	F2156	188	25°54' 92°0'	O ₃ ~ 60 ppb, CO ~ 160 ppb
1820	"	F2104	188	25°18' 92°0'	At this southern end extensive filled-in cumulus streets, largely Sc
182216	Inter- upt	8000'			Interupt to turn at southern end and continue north
182410	Recon- merce	8000'	353	25°12' 92°0'	Pretty thick Sc
1829		2600'	"	25°30' 92°0'	nearing Sc tops: - 2000 ft base ~ 800 ft
183205		50 feet			PCASP steady ~ 500 both SID probes reading particles
183213	R8	100 ft	008		183305 copious oil on surface
					sea state: a few whitecaps (force 4?) Helmann 25.4°C
1837	"	"	359	26°6' 92°0'	Having been under Sc, now clearer overhead
1840	"	"	002	26°18' 91°54'	Looks like complete clear skies
1844	"	"	000	26°42' 91°54'	T = 24.6 Td 24.5 Wind 8ms ⁻¹ /144°
1848					PCASP steady ~ 450, AMS steady
					Helmann has dropped 24.6 ↓ 24.5 °C 25.4

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.292**

 Date **4/5/07**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
185359	(K8)	100'	002	27°11'N 91°54'W	Beautifully clear at this end of run
185535		"		27°18'N 91°54'W	Swip to port, we go through plume / wake
1856					Copious oil on surface
					Neph, AMS do not register much
1858	"	"	005	27°24'N 91°54'W	Helmann down to 24°C
185840	end R8	100'		27°30'N 92°	Some patchy CuSc just here, coming overhead
190122	P8	400' A			
190630	P↑	6000'			O3 27 ppb CO 148.3 ppb
1919	P↑	20FL250	182	26°18'N 92°0'	CuSc to port, clear to Sb below Air traffic restricting us to FL240
192241	end P8 start R9	FL240	188	26°0'N 92°0'	Extensive Sc to port short run before Aqua overpass run
192540	end R9	"		25°42'N 92°0'	
192717	R10	FL240	346	25°48'N 91°54'W	Sonde #11 192800 {in sea at 1938}
192920		"	353	26°0'N 91°54'W	"clear sky below + above" - Alessio
193020					ARIES: "cloud below"
					Sonde #12 193100 {at 5700' at 1938}
					Helmann seems to operate ok at FL240 whereas it has been failing at FL300
					Sonde #13 193359 {at 12900' at 1938}
193435	(R10)	FL240	357	26°24'N 92°0'	T -22.7°C T _d -50.2 Wind 7ms / 256° looks clear below
					Sonde #14 193601 {at 18,500' at 1938}
					Sonde #15 194000
1942			357	27°6'N 92°0'	MARSS: moist below, dry above
194250					SWS sees sees cloud below (Cu streaks)
	end R10				Sonde #16 194500 (115 total)
					In total? JAVEX

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B292 **T/O:** 14:59:52
Date of flight: 04/05/07 **Land:** 20:37:34

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to processing PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		hh = Last sec processed =
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		File size =
3) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (see comment box)</i> e) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Use time just before/after take-off/landing. If T/O /landing just after/before the hour, ensure start/end time is before/after the hour if there is an FFSSP_hh.txt file for that hour.
4) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: <i>Use the most recent calibration file.</i> Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)		Total glitches = Sec file written ok? Note calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) FLOODS> WAVE a) WAVE> write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto b) WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Note time correction applied to FFSSP by /auto =
6) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY (y=x+1) d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		Input file size = M5 output file size =
7) CHECKS: i). Are FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC synchronized in time? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>JW LWC para 535</i> <i>Nevzorov LWC para 602</i> <i>FFSSP LWC para 1202</i> ii). If not, repeat from step 5b replacing /auto with addt=x which adds x+20 secs to FFSSP time.		Synchronized?

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B292
Date of Flight: 04/05/07

B) 2D PROCESSING		REPROCESS +1hr
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC		Y
2) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)		Y
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS	Y	Y
4) Log on to FLOODS		
5) Unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.zip	Y	Size of Bnnn.dat = 181321
6) FLOODS> WAVE WAVE> CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat WAVE> exit	Y	Use PVWAVE for this section Blocks read = 48158 Blocks written = 48158 Bad reads = 0
7) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 5 min)</i> f) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land + 5 min)</i> g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data: Y j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: Y l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N	Y	Start = 145500 End = 204500 Ignore error message scroll (vestigial error from tapes) Are FRW, FSP, IMB, PCA,SEC files in PMSDATA? Y Are they non-zero in size? Y
8) FLOODS> WAVE i). WAVE> imagedisplay a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) File generation no: 0 d) Time from IWC plot: N e) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP f) Start time: <i>As in 7e above</i> g) End time: <i>As in 7f above</i> h) Time interval (sec): 5 recommended (0 for all images) ii). WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 1 min)</i> e) Enter end time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 1 min)</i> f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks: 10 iii). WAVE> exit to create files iv). FTP ascii *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC v). Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter vi). Output as pdf file (720 dpi resolution), appending name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files	Y	2D image display and printing Must be done from FLOODS itself. Note any problems with images 2DC 150220-150300 only 2DP noise only Prepare imagery for Core data From own PC again Start = 145500 End = 204500 FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_ Bnnn_2Dx-images.ps Notes on this in instructions

<p>9) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO</p> <p>a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: <i>Hit enter</i> d) Time correction: <i>Time offset of the 2D data</i> e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both <i>0 unless either probe known to be faulty</i> h) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O + 30sec)</i> i) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 30sec)</i> j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type 2DC: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud l) Particle type 2DP: 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown m) Coefficient choice: 2 n) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D</p>	Y	<p>NB. an error message may appear, floating point exception, rerun and use time quoted in error message, repeat until successful.</p> <p>X = A</p> <p>Start = 150000 End = 203500</p> <p>Time data processed to = 203741 2dproc files present? Y *.2dc, *.2dp and *.dat</p>
<p>10) FLOODS> WAVE</p> <p>i) WAVE> WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D' ii). exit</p>	Y	<p>Use PVWAVE for this section</p> <p>Error message about HDDR file should be ignored. Records = 1762, 178</p>
<p>11) FLOODS> MODIFY</p> <p>a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default</p>	Y	<p>X = _tas Y = (X+1) = _tas_2d</p>
<p>12) CHECKS:</p> <p>Are 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Nevzerov TWC para 605</i> <i>2DC IWC para 1302</i> <i>2DP IWC para 1312</i></p>	N	<p>Data present in mfd</p> <p>Correlated?</p>

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B292
Date of Flight: 04/05/07

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:	Y	
2) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: Bnnn b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: <i>default = 1</i> <i>If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here</i> e) Calibration volume flow rate: <i>Use the most recent value. 1.8ccs⁻¹</i> <i>Calibration files to be stored in Exeter</i> <i>Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm³s⁻¹</i> f) Time correction: <i>Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9d</i> g) Start time: <i>0 if unknown</i> h) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>	Y	Min size = 2 Vol flow rate = 0.8 150000 203700
3) FLOODS> WAVE i).WAVE> write_procpcasp_to_m5, 'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp' ii). WAVE> exit	Y	Use PVWAVE for this section
4) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>	Y	X = _tas_2d Y = X+1 = _tas_2dpcasp
5) CHECKS Are PCASP and JW peaks synchronous? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>JW LWC para 535</i> <i>PCASP conc para 1550</i>	N	Data present in mfd Merged OK?

FAAM Dropsonde Flight Log

Flight No.	B292	Date	4 May 2007
Page No.	1 of 2	Operator	Doug Anderson

GMT	Sonde No.	Event	Comments
		<i>e.g. launch, splashdown</i>	<i>e.g. wind data? PTH data? Lat/Long NB strings of dropsonde data contain: time, pressure hPa, T deg C, RH %, wind direction deg, wind speed m/s, longitude, latitude, height m</i>
			Sondes 1-8 launched around the 1546Z MetOp satellite overpass
15:43:06	1	Launch	359.20 -28.10 12.94 275.60 12.20 -18.60 -91.969700 27.532700 7936.70
15:52:52	1	splashdown	9999.00 99.00 999.00 137.44 7.43 -11.20 -91.939025 27.560037 99999.00
15:44:57	2	Launch	359.20 -28.20 13.21 274.30 13.10 -18.30 -91.980700 27.371200 7937.00
15:54:57	2	splashdown	1011.92 24.59 93.45 138.80 9.18 -11.35 -91.951006 27.389673 99999.00 Occ GPS loss through most of flight
15:46:54	3	Launch	359.40 -28.00 12.54 275.50 12.40 -17.40 -91.991300 27.200600 7934.70
15:56:51	3	splashdown	1012.05 24.42 94.53 133.13 9.15 -11.99 -91.962048 27.214186 99999.00
15:48:54	4	Launch	359.40 -27.90 12.42 275.40 12.10 -16.80 -91.997800 27.017600 7933.00
15:59:05	4	splashdown	1011.94 24.53 96.97 137.63 7.18 -7.98 -91.969185 27.035097 99999.00
15:54:36	5	Launch	359.70 -27.70 10.76 274.20 10.40 -17.40 -92.001100 26.489300 7928.50
16:04:23	5	splashdown	1011.36 24.73 95.56 132.42 8.44 -10.89 -91.973764 26.519361 99999.00
16:01:27	6	Launch	359.40 -27.80 8.83 272.20 10.70 -17.50 -92.000100 25.874900 7933.30
16:11:28	6	splashdown	1011.46 25.31 90.70 146.08 9.51 -11.39 -91.974932 25.892976 99999.00 Occ gps dropout at mid drop altitudes
16:22:42	7	Launch	343.90 -30.80 10.65 304.40 8.80 -17.30 -92.000700 25.692300 8236.90
16:33:10	7	splashdown	1011.43 25.22 92.81 142.66 8.67 -11.32 -91.975532 25.714308 99999.00 Some GPS dropouts mid drop
16:28:33	8	Launch	344.10 -30.70 13.16 327.80 11.20 -17.20 -92.000800 26.214100 8233.30
16:38:48	8	splashdown	1011.22 25.12 92.39 142.33 8.98 -11.53 -91.971948 26.231160 99999.00
			Sondes 9-10 launched during aircraft inter-comparison runs
16:59:35	9	Launch	356.87 5.79 0.45 357.83 96.05 -0.00 -91.999758 26.409896 8410.46
17:09:24	9	splashdown	1010.50 25.09 92.64 146.69 8.74 -11.60 -91.972113 26.427313 41.28 No Launch detect
17:39:33	10	Launch	359.20 -27.90 8.11 321.70 11.20 -16.20 -92.000100 26.423600 7937.00
17:49:31	10	splashdown	1010.14 24.92 92.73 144.45 9.66 -11.52 -91.971226 26.439771 99999.00

Flight No.	B292	Date	4 May 2007
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GMT	Sonde No.	Event	Comments
		<i>e.g. launch, splashdown</i>	<i>e.g. wind data? PTH data? Lat/Long NB strings of dropsonde data contain: time, pressure hPa, T deg C, RH %, wind direction deg, wind speed m/s, longitude, latitude, height m</i>
			Sondes 11-16 launched around the 19:38Z AQUA satellite overpass
192803	11	Launch	392.00 -22.70 5.38 277.30 7.70 -13.60 -91.976500 25.922100 7328.10
193733	11	splashdown	1010.96 25.30 93.07 144.33 8.96 -11.56 -91.955597 25.941732 99999.00
193103	12	Launch	392.30 -22.50 6.00 271.60 7.30 -13.50 -91.995200 26.176300 7322.50
194029	12	splashdown	1003.69 24.74 95.45 143.62 7.70 -8.41 -91.972192 26.194774 -296.51
193403	13	Launch	392.50 -22.50 6.07 262.20 8.20 -13.90 -92.000200 26.434000 7318.90
194334	13	splashdown	1010.08 24.91 93.49 147.04 8.74 -11.93 -91.975211 26.452170 99999.00
193603	14	Launch	392.40 -22.90 7.30 253.50 7.90 -14.20 -92.000100 26.601300 7321.20
194530	14	splashdown	1011.11 24.86 93.55 144.50 8.48 -11.47 -91.975291 26.620819 99999.00
194003	15	Launch	392.30 -23.00 10.42 247.90 8.10 -14.40 -92.000400 26.938000 7321.30
194927	15	splashdown	1010.92 24.65 94.90 136.86 9.67 -11.91 -91.974651 26.957855 99999.00
194524	16	Launch	392.20 -23.50 13.99 266.80 8.80 -13.90 -92.000300 27.385100 7323.70
195417	16	splashdown	1010.63 24.85 93.83 144.60 10.05 -11.73 1010.64 -91.975052 27.373648 99999.00 Late Launch detect
	17	Launch	
	17	splashdown	
	18	Launch	
	18	splashdown	
	19	Launch	
	19	splashdown	
	20	Launch	
	20	splashdown	

B292 CVI log

5/4/07	2:41:45 PM	144104	gnd zero
5/4/07	3:12:04 PM		adjusted pcasp flows
5/4/07	3:20:27 PM		zero at FL240
5/4/07	3:37:41 PM		zero at FL260
5/4/07	4:13:33 PM		zero at FL270
5/4/07	4:55:44 PM		zero at FL260
5/4/07	5:20:10 PM		zero at FL270
5/4/07	5:34:02 PM		zero at FL260
5/4/07	5:58:18 PM		zero at FL270
5/4/07	6:25:25 PM		zero at FL070
5/4/07	7:14:26 PM		zero at FL150
5/4/07	7:14:27 PM		zero at FL150
5/4/07	7:23:11 PM		zero at FL240
5/4/07	7:47:30 PM		zero at FL240

B292_SWS_SHIMS_EventLog.txt

```

13:45:21.24 --- - - - -
13:45:21.24 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
13:45:21.24 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
                               tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
13:45:21.24 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B292
13:45:21.24 --- - - - -
13:45:49.86 SWS - - - - Initialising: VIS OK NIR OK
13:45:54.25 USH - - - - Initialising: VIS OK NIR OK
13:45:57.74 LSH - - - - Initialising: VIS OK NIR OK
13:46:02.68 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
13:46:05.89 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
13:46:09.08 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
13:46:18.89 SWS - - 350 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 350ms.
13:46:24.48 SWS - - - 350 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 350ms.
13:46:31.50 USH - - 400 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 400ms.
13:46:35.38 USH - - - 400 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 400ms.
13:46:39.48 LSH - - 400 - VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 400ms.
13:46:43.12 LSH - - - 400 NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 400ms.
13:46:54.91 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:46:54.91 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:46:54.92 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:47:02.64 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:47:02.90 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:47:02.94 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:47:06.57 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:47:07.34 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:47:07.54 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:47:33.51 LSH - - 990 - VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 990ms.
13:47:37.94 LSH - - - 990 NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 990ms.
15:02:01.52 SWS 174R - - - - Telescope position set to 174R
15:02:06.87 USH - - 200 - VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 200ms.
15:02:13.16 USH - - - 990 NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 990ms.
15:02:20.66 SWS - - - 750 NIR int.time changed from 350ms to 750ms.
15:02:27.44 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:02:27.88 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:02:27.90 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:02:35.37 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:02:38.22 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:02:38.47 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:03:44.23 LSH - - 350 - VIS int.time changed from 990ms to 350ms.
15:03:49.33 LSH - - 200 - VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 200ms.
15:03:54.87 USH - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
15:04:00.39 USH - - - 500 NIR int.time changed from 990ms to 500ms.
15:04:05.70 SWS - - 200 - VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 200ms.
15:04:12.48 SWS - - 75 - VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 75ms.
15:04:19.23 SWS - - 50 - VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 50ms.
15:04:23.85 SWS - - - 250 NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 250ms.
15:04:28.77 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:04:28.92 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:04:28.92 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:04:31.95 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:04:34.62 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:04:39.12 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:09:34.97 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:09:35.14 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:09:35.19 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
15:09:37.96 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:09:40.62 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:09:45.74 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
15:20:05.49 --- - - - - *** Start of run 1
15:20:08.99 SWS 174R - - - - Telescope position set to 174R
15:20:13.71 SWS - - 250 - VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 250ms.
15:20:18.68 SWS - - - 750 NIR int.time changed from 250ms to 750ms.
15:20:24.58 LSH - - 300 - VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 300ms.
15:20:32.17 LSH - - 500 - VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 500ms.
15:20:38.21 LSH - - 990 - VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 990ms.
15:20:42.13 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.

```

15:20:42.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:20:42.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:20:47.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:20:50.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:20:52.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:23:22.90	LSH	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 990ms to 350ms.
15:23:27.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:23:38.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:25:12.56	---	-	-	-	-	*** banking in run interrupt
15:25:42.05	---	-	-	-	-	*** run restart
15:25:47.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:25:48.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:25:48.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:25:52.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:25:56.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:25:58.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:30:29.28	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 75ms.
15:30:32.98	SWS	-	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 300ms.
15:30:36.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:30:39.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:30:41.14	LSH	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 300ms.
15:30:46.44	LSH	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 250ms.
15:30:48.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:30:58.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:31:36.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:31:36.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:31:37.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:31:39.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:31:41.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:31:47.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:34:47.04	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
15:34:51.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:34:51.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:34:52.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:34:54.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:34:57.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:35:02.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:38:00.44	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run 2
15:38:05.18	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 200ms.
15:38:11.62	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 250ms.
15:38:15.33	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 750ms.
15:38:20.46	LSH	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 750ms.
15:38:27.09	LSH	-	-	990	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 990ms.
15:38:30.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:38:30.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:38:30.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:38:36.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:38:38.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:38:41.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:38:54.57	LSH	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 990ms to 500ms.
15:38:59.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:39:10.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:41:53.48	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
15:41:57.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:41:57.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:41:57.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:42:03.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:42:05.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:42:08.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:43:04.33	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run 2.2
15:46:33.98	---	-	-	-	-	*** metop overpass
15:49:03.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:49:03.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:49:03.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:49:08.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:49:11.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:49:13.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:51:32.02	LSH	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 400ms.
15:51:34.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

15:51:34.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:51:34.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:51:39.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:51:42.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:51:44.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:52:28.16	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 50ms.
15:52:31.52	SWS	-	-	-	350	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 350ms.
15:52:39.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:52:43.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:53:06.89	LSH	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 350ms.
15:53:10.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:53:21.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:54:17.62	---	-	-	-	-	*** over wave sc / streets of sc
15:56:18.60	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 250ms.
15:56:23.39	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 350ms to 750ms.
15:56:31.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:56:39.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:57:44.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:57:44.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:57:44.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:57:50.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:57:52.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:57:55.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:03:36.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:03:37.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:03:37.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:03:42.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:03:45.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:03:47.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:08:20.52	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 75ms.
16:08:25.37	SWS	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 400ms.
16:08:28.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:08:28.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:08:28.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:08:33.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:08:33.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:08:34.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:08:38.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:11:04.34	---	-	-	-	-	*** banking in run
16:11:52.60	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
16:11:55.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:11:55.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:11:55.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:11:59.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:12:01.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:12:05.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:12:30.21	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
16:12:39.35	---	-	-	-	-	*** for start ofrun
16:12:49.63	SWS	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 350ms.
16:12:54.81	SWS	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 500ms.
16:12:58.55	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 750ms.
16:14:20.41	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run 3.1
16:14:22.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:14:22.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:14:22.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:14:27.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:14:30.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:14:33.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:16:41.92	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
16:16:46.26	SWS	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 350ms.
16:16:51.29	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 250ms.
16:16:57.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:16:58.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:16:58.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:17:03.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:17:06.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:17:08.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:17:20.80	SWS	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 150ms.
16:17:25.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

16:17:33.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:20:14.59	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 75ms.
16:20:17.29	SWS	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 400ms.
16:20:19.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:20:24.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:20:50.66	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
16:20:56.07	SWS	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 400ms.
16:21:00.38	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 750ms.
16:21:05.75	SWS	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 500ms.
16:21:13.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:21:13.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:21:13.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:21:18.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:21:21.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:21:23.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:22:22.73	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
16:22:26.76	SWS	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 300ms.
16:22:31.08	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 200ms.
16:22:35.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:22:36.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:22:36.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:22:41.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:22:44.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:22:46.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:26:23.02	SWS	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 300ms.
16:26:30.07	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
16:26:31.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:26:32.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:26:32.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:26:36.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:26:40.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:26:42.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:28:01.91	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 250ms.
16:28:07.96	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
16:28:10.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:28:10.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:28:10.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:28:15.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:28:18.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:28:20.47	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:31:43.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:31:44.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:31:44.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:31:49.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:31:51.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:31:54.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:32:07.17	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 100ms.
16:32:10.44	SWS	-	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 300ms.
16:32:18.27	SWS	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 300ms.
16:32:26.94	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 200ms.
16:32:29.92	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 750ms.
16:32:32.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:32:40.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:32:52.70	SWS	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 350ms.
16:32:59.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:32:59.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:32:59.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:33:05.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:33:07.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:33:10.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:34:02.04	SWS	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 300ms.
16:34:05.27	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
16:34:09.65	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 250ms.
16:34:14.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:34:15.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:34:15.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:34:20.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:34:23.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:34:25.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

16:35:43.75	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 100ms.
16:35:53.86	SWS	-	-	-	350	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 350ms.
16:35:59.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:36:03.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:36:09.50	LSH	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 300ms.
16:38:49.10	SWS	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 300ms.
16:38:53.90	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 350ms to 750ms.
16:38:56.37	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
16:38:57.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:38:57.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:38:57.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:39:03.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:39:05.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:39:08.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:39:56.33	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
16:40:00.99	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 200ms.
16:40:10.01	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
16:40:16.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:40:16.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:40:16.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:40:21.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:40:24.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:40:26.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:43:13.54	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
16:46:39.77	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run 3.2
16:46:43.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:46:43.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:46:43.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:46:48.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:46:51.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:46:54.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:47:12.42	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
16:47:23.57	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 250ms.
16:47:28.93	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 200ms.
16:47:34.62	USH	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 75ms.
16:47:38.25	USH	-	-	-	350	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 350ms.
16:47:42.32	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
16:47:48.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:47:54.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:47:56.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:47:56.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:47:58.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:48:06.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:51:03.97	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
16:51:09.92	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 250ms.
16:51:14.31	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 200ms.
16:51:19.80	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:51:20.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:51:20.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:51:23.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:51:28.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:51:30.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:52:47.63	SWS	-	-	15	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 15ms.
16:52:52.35	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 15ms to 50ms.
16:52:55.55	SWS	-	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 300ms.
16:53:00.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:53:03.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:53:05.03	LSH	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 250ms.
16:53:07.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:53:17.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:54:14.05	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
16:54:18.93	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
16:54:22.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:54:26.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:54:43.03	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
16:54:50.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:54:50.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:54:51.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:54:53.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

16:54:54.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:55:01.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:55:30.58	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run 4
16:55:59.41	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
16:56:01.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:56:01.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:56:01.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:56:05.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:56:05.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:56:11.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:56:37.43	LSH	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 350ms.
16:56:41.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:56:51.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:59:29.55	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
16:59:31.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:59:31.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:59:31.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:59:35.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:59:35.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:59:41.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:59:41.80	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 750ms.
16:59:45.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:59:53.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:06:41.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:06:41.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:06:42.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:06:45.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:06:49.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:06:52.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:09:22.84	SWS	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 150ms.
17:09:26.95	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 100ms.
17:09:32.67	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
17:09:33.00	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
17:09:35.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:09:35.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:09:35.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:09:39.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:09:42.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:09:46.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:14:15.56	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
17:14:23.24	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 200ms.
17:14:27.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:14:28.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:14:28.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:14:32.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:14:35.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:14:38.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:17:49.65	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
17:17:52.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:17:53.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:17:53.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:17:56.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:18:01.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:18:03.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:20:27.47	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run 5
17:20:36.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:20:37.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:20:40.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:20:41.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:20:44.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:20:50.79	SWS	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 150ms.
17:20:51.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:21:03.78	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
17:21:09.22	SWS	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 300ms.
17:21:14.19	SWS	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 150ms.
17:21:19.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:21:19.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:21:19.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:21:23.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

17:21:27.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:21:31.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:21:46.89	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 100ms.
17:21:50.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:21:58.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:22:43.34	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
17:22:47.81	SWS	-	-	-	350	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 350ms.
17:22:51.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:22:55.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:23:04.54	SWS	-	-	15	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 15ms.
17:23:09.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:23:13.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:25:10.95	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
17:25:14.68	LSH	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 300ms.
17:25:18.01	SWS	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 15ms to 300ms.
17:25:24.48	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 200ms.
17:25:26.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:25:26.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:25:27.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:25:30.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:25:30.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:25:37.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:25:43.88	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
17:25:47.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:25:47.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:25:48.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:25:51.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:25:52.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:25:59.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:29:18.96	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
17:29:22.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:29:22.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:29:23.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:29:27.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:29:27.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:29:33.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:32:28.69	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
17:32:32.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:32:32.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:32:32.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:32:36.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:32:36.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:32:43.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:33:19.30	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run 6
17:33:26.39	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
17:33:42.96	SWS	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 300ms.
17:33:46.19	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 250ms.
17:33:50.34	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 200ms.
17:33:56.40	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 350ms to 750ms.
17:34:06.50	LSH	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 350ms.
17:34:08.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:34:09.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:34:09.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:34:12.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:34:17.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:34:19.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:37:28.43	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
17:37:36.07	SWS	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 350ms.
17:37:40.34	SWS	-	-	-	350	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 350ms.
17:37:51.92	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 100ms.
17:37:56.94	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
17:37:59.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:38:00.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:38:00.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:38:03.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:38:04.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:38:11.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:43:24.13	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
17:43:30.86	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 200ms.

17:43:35.51	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 350ms to 750ms.
17:43:42.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:43:43.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:43:43.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:43:46.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:43:51.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:43:53.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:44:49.44	LSH	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 400ms.
17:44:57.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:45:07.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:48:21.31	SWS	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 150ms.
17:48:26.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:48:26.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:48:26.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:48:26.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:48:30.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
17:48:33.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:48:36.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:48:46.81	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
17:48:52.62	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 75ms.
17:48:57.03	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 50ms.
17:49:33.04	LSH	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 350ms.
17:49:35.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:49:46.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:50:16.67	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
17:50:20.72	LSH	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 300ms.
17:50:25.02	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 250ms.
17:50:29.20	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 200ms.
17:50:32.67	SWS	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 150ms.
17:50:36.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:50:37.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:50:37.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:50:40.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
17:50:45.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:50:46.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:50:47.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:50:54.89	LSH	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 200ms.
17:50:59.02	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 50ms.
17:51:02.45	SWS	-	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 300ms.
17:51:06.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:51:10.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:52:33.03	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
17:56:59.27	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run
17:57:01.10	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 200ms.
17:57:08.33	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 750ms.
17:57:24.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:57:24.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:57:24.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:57:28.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:57:32.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:57:35.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:58:55.23	LSH	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 350ms.
18:01:52.16	LSH	-	-	500	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 500ms.
18:01:57.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:01:57.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:01:58.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:02:01.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:02:05.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:02:08.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:07:19.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:07:19.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:07:19.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:07:23.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:07:27.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:07:30.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:07:47.60	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
18:11:37.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:11:37.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:11:37.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

18:11:41.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:11:45.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:11:47.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:17:11.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:17:12.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:17:12.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:17:16.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:17:20.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:17:22.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:21:59.03	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 75ms.
18:22:01.87	SWS	-	-	-	300	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 300ms.
18:22:06.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:22:06.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:22:06.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:22:09.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:22:10.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:22:17.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:28:56.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:28:56.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:28:56.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:28:59.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:29:00.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:29:06.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:30:58.42	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
18:31:02.60	SWS	-	-	15	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 15ms.
18:31:07.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:31:07.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:31:07.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:31:11.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:31:11.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:31:17.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:32:28.35	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run
18:32:32.89	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 200ms.
18:32:37.68	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 100ms.
18:32:42.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:32:43.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:32:50.35	LSH	-	-	750	-	VIS int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
18:32:56.23	LSH	-	-	990	-	VIS int.time changed from 750ms to 990ms.
18:33:03.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:33:14.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:37:05.57	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
18:37:11.74	SWS	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 15ms to 400ms.
18:37:16.94	SWS	-	-	-	500	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 500ms.
18:37:22.01	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 500ms to 750ms.
18:37:25.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:37:25.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:37:25.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:37:30.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:37:33.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:37:36.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:37:46.28	SWS	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 350ms.
18:38:21.02	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 250ms.
18:38:25.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:38:33.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:42:04.25	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
18:42:07.82	SWS	-	-	75	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 75ms.
18:42:15.97	SWS	-	-	-	150	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 150ms.
18:42:22.83	SWS	-	-	15	-	VIS int.time changed from 75ms to 15ms.
18:42:27.75	SWS	-	-	-	200	NIR int.time changed from 150ms to 200ms.
18:42:31.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:42:31.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:42:32.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:42:34.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:42:36.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:42:42.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:42:49.75	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 15ms to 50ms.
18:42:54.18	SWS	-	-	15	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 15ms.
18:43:01.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:43:03.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

18:46:22.86	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
18:46:31.16	SWS	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 15ms to 300ms.
18:46:38.23	SWS	-	-	-	400	NIR int.time changed from 200ms to 400ms.
18:46:43.75	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 400ms to 750ms.
18:46:48.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:46:49.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:46:49.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:46:53.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:46:57.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:46:59.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:50:24.28	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
18:50:30.15	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 50ms.
18:50:33.05	SWS	-	-	-	150	NIR int.time changed from 750ms to 150ms.
18:50:39.03	SWS	-	-	15	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 15ms.
18:51:03.86	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 25ms to 100ms.
18:51:06.60	SWS	-	-	25	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 25ms.
18:51:11.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:51:12.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:51:12.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:51:14.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:51:16.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:51:22.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:55:07.79	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
18:55:16.36	SWS	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 25ms to 200ms.
18:55:22.70	SWS	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 200ms to 350ms.
18:55:26.62	SWS	-	-	-	250	NIR int.time changed from 150ms to 250ms.
18:55:30.15	SWS	-	-	-	750	NIR int.time changed from 250ms to 750ms.
18:55:36.51	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
18:55:42.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:55:42.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:55:43.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:55:46.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:55:51.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:55:53.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:57:47.98	SWS	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 300ms.
18:57:50.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:57:58.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:58:45.06	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
18:58:48.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:58:49.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:58:49.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:58:53.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:58:57.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:58:59.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:13:15.26	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 250ms.
19:13:17.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:13:17.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:13:18.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:13:21.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:13:26.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:13:27.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:19:20.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:19:20.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:19:20.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:19:23.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:19:28.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:19:30.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:23:08.42	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run 9
19:23:12.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:23:13.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:23:13.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:23:17.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:23:21.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:23:23.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:25:50.19	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
19:25:53.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:25:53.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:25:53.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:25:57.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

19:26:01.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:26:03.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:27:31.08	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run 9.2
19:27:40.28	LSH	-	-	400	-	VIS int.time changed from 990ms to 400ms.
19:27:45.30	LSH	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 400ms to 350ms.
19:27:48.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:27:48.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:27:48.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:27:52.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:27:57.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:27:59.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:29:24.27	---	-	-	-	-	*** above should read run 10
19:33:18.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:33:18.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:33:18.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:33:22.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:33:26.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:33:28.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:38:05.05	---	-	-	-	-	*** aqua overpass
19:38:36.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:38:36.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:38:36.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:38:40.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:38:44.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:38:46.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:43:51.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:43:51.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:43:51.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:43:55.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:43:59.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:44:02.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:44:14.51	---	-	-	-	-	*** over 2/8 sc5
19:50:59.55	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
19:51:05.99	SWS	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 350ms.
19:51:09.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:51:09.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:51:09.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:51:13.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:51:17.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:51:20.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:55:54.76	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
19:55:59.05	SWS	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 300ms.
19:56:03.49	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 250ms.
19:56:06.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:56:06.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:56:07.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:56:11.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:56:14.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:56:17.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:56:59.07	SWS	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 150ms.
19:57:03.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:57:12.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:57:13.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:00:58.64	LSH	-	-	300	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 300ms.
20:01:02.48	SWS	6F	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 6F
20:01:11.93	SWS	-	-	350	-	VIS int.time changed from 150ms to 350ms.
20:01:18.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:01:18.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:01:18.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:01:22.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:01:26.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:01:29.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:01:45.28	LSH	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 250ms.
20:01:48.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:01:49.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:01:49.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:01:52.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:01:57.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:01:59.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

20:02:22.09	LSH	-	-	200	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 200ms.
20:02:24.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:02:35.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:05:58.13	SWS	174R	-	-	-	Telescope position set to 174R
20:06:01.66	SWS	-	-	250	-	VIS int.time changed from 350ms to 250ms.
20:06:08.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:06:08.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:06:09.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:06:13.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:06:16.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:06:19.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:08:15.24	SWS	-	-	150	-	VIS int.time changed from 250ms to 150ms.
20:08:17.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:08:25.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:08:56.79	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of
20:09:21.12	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run - end of science
20:09:35.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
20:09:38.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
20:09:41.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
20:09:50.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Instrument closed.
20:09:54.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Instrument closed.
20:09:55.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Instrument closed.

ARIES flight log

Flight: B292

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Date: 4/5/07

Operator(s): JSS

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: JAIYEX Gulf of Mexico Intercompensation

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Sht	HBB	CBB	Comments
152921							Started house keeping
152414	R1.1	1/120	HRB	clsd	7064	3055	
152739	R1.2	1/120	HRB	clsd	7079	3055	
153204	R1.2	1/60	cal	clsd	7081	3049	
153325	R1.2	500/1	Nwd	clsd	7071	3072	over str cu steel. ended S3 3040
153513	P1	1/60	cal	clsd	709	3046	
153812	R2.	1/60	cal	clsd	7064	3037	
153448		360/1	Nwd	clsd	7072	3067	clear below. end 154152
154250		1/60	cal	clsd	7078	3054	
154280							
154407	R2.2	480/1	Nwd	clsd	7072	3067	Clear below over pass 01546
154907	R2.2	1/60	cal	clsd	7072	3053	
154922	R2.2	480/1	Nwd	clsd	7078	3045	
155322	R2.2	1/60	cal	clsd	7079	3068	
155439	R2.2	480/1	Nwd	clsd	7073	3032	
155854	R2.2	1/60	cal	clsd	7074	3055	
160061	R2.2	480/1	Nwd	clsd	7069	3072	
160443	R2.2	1/60	cal	clsd	7059	3071	
160556	R2.2	360/1	Nwd	clsd	7047	3031	
160901	R2.2	1/60	cal	clsd	7072	3065	
161354	end R2.2	1/60	cal	clsd	7067	3068	
161510	R3-B	120/1	Zen	open	7013	2979	
161620	R3-B	360/1	Nwd	clsd	7079	3069	
161824	R3-B	1/60	cal	clsd	7059	3062	
162043	R3-B	120/1	Zen	open	7074	3029	
162156	R3-B	360/1	Nwd	clsd	7071	3048	
162456	R3-B	1/60	cal	clsd	7059	3021	
162525	R3-B	120/1	Zen	open	7022	3065	
162732	R3-B	360/1	Nwd	clsd	7091	3062	Clear below.
163054	R3-B	1/60	cal	clsd	7070	3061	
163225	R3-B	360/1	Zen	open	7074		
163400	R2.3	360/1	Nwd	cl	7079	3061	

ARIES flight log			Flight: B292	page 2 of
Date: 4/05/06	Operator(s): CS85	Res: 1	Gain A: CB2	
Loc./Notes:				

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
163711	R3-3	1/60	cal	clsd			
163824	R3-3	120/1	Zen	open	7056	30-26	
163933	R3-3	360/1	Ned	clsd	7073	30-51	
164525	R3-2	1/60	cal	clsd			
164525	end R3-2	1/60	cal	clsd	7066	30-28	
164650	R3-2	360/1	Zen	open	7085	30-62	Clear above.
165005	R3-2	1/60	cal	clsd	7015	31-06	
165126	R3-2	360/1	Ned	clsd	7097	30-38	end KZS18
165227	R3-2	1/60	Prop	open			ZHCNCHZ x3 opened shutter late.
155443	end R3-2	1/60	cal	clsd	6877	30-28	
165602	R4	360/1	Zen	open	69-35	30-52	
165902	R4	1/60	cal	clsd	70-17	30-14	
170017	R4	360/1	Ned	clsd	7077	30-20	
170319	R4	1/60	cal	clsd	7060	30-26	
170428	R4			open			Propile ZHCNCHZ x3
170825	R4	1/60	cal	clsd	68-36	30-58	
170912	R4	360/1	Zen	open	70-39	30-3	
171243	R4	1/60	cal	clsd	70-11	30-54	
171358	R4	360/1	Ned	clsd	70-39	30-33	
171701	R4	1/60	cal	clsd	70-26	31-39	end of run 4
172003	R5	1/60	cal	clsd	7068	30-6	
172054	R5	360/1	Zen	open	70-3	30-14	
172346	R5	1/60	cal	clsd	70-28	30-70	
172913	R5	360/1	Ned	clsd			
172814	R5	1/60	cal	clsd	70-82	30-92	
172932	R5	360/1	Zen	open	70-17	30-86	173230
173244	end R5	1/60	cal	clsd	70-30	30-60	
173555	R6	360/1	Ned	clsd	7068	30-6	
173687	R6	1/60	cal	clsd	7029	30-22	
173813	R6	360/1	Zen	open	70-24	30-82	Clear below above
174115	R6	1/60	cal	clsd	69-11	30-19	

ARIES flight log

Flight: B292

page 3 of

Date: 04/05/07

Operator(s): JSS

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: JAVEX

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
174227	R8		open		70.3	31.42	Profile ZHCNCHZ & J
174443	R8	1/60	clsd	cal	69.8	30.80	- HBB cold.
174904	R8	180/1	open	zen	70.0	30.63	short run
175044	R8	180/1	clsd	Nov	70.8	30.49	wave seen below.
175211	R8	1/120	clsd	cal	70.66	30.50	
175710	R7		open				Profile ZHCNCHZ x3 end 1807510
183121	R2 end	1/60	clsd	cal	70.43	30.61	
183235	R8	300/1	zen	open	70.41	30.65	
183555	R2	1/60	cal	clsd	70.32	32.24	
183714	R2	300/1	Nov	clsd	70.55	32.39	
184026	R8	1/60	cal	clsd	70.85	32.46	CBB warming up
184145	un	360/1	zen	open	70.0	32.55	Clear down
184501	un	1/60	cal	clsd	70.45	33.26	
184618	un	360/1	Nov	clsd	71.03	34.35	
184923	un	1/60	cal	clsd	70.97	34.4	
185042	un	360/1	zen	open	70.2	34.46	
185249	un	1/60	cal	clsd	70.5	36.42	
185816	un	360/1	Nov	clsd	71.07	36.0	
185817	un	1/60	cal	clsd	70.98	35.98	
190631	R10	1/60	cal	clsd	70.89	31.01	
192743	R10	480/1	Nov	clsd	70.79	30.77	
193148	R10	1/60	cal	clsd	70.77	30.50	
193301	R10	480/1	Nov	clsd	70.79	30.62	ended 193522 early ready for
193536	R10	1/60	cal	clsd	70.85	30.70	comp
193649	R10	480/1	Nov	clsd	70.83	30.46	
194052	R10	1/60	cal	clsd	70.80	30.3	
194215	R10	480/1	Nov	clsd	70.81	30.61	
194628	R10	1/60	cal	clsd	70.62	31.03	
194919	R11	1/60	cal	clsd	70.80	31.31	

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	04/05/07	Flight	B292	log pages	2
Operator(s)	Pollard		Campaign	JAIVEX			
Departure	Ellington Field		Arrival	Ellington Field			

System start

MARSS

Visual pod inspection							X
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers							X
Close all MARSS circuit breakers							X
FERA on				at time	12:41:44		
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	25.0°C	Ch	24.8°C	Ch18	24.7°C	
Temperature controller set points		54°C	17	58°C	-20	40°C	
MARSS CPU on				at time	12:41:52		
Initial target temperatures	Hot	297.8	Cold	297.3			
Target heating							X
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***							X
Scanning on (LMD box)				at time	12:45:36		
Scan indication			Monitor)		Visual	X

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers							
Turn on Deimos CPU							
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***							
Start Deimos Software				at time			
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold				
Target heating							
Scan indication			Monitor			Visual	
Weather	Cloud		Precip				
	Surface		Pressure				
	Other						

System functionality check

(after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC} = t_{DRS} +$	0	at time	14:42:27			
Brightness temps 'sensible'							X
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	344.64	Cold	300.97		
	Deimos:	Hot		Cold			
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B			
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)			
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20		
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)		
	1	34.27	36.56	40.26	40.69		

Power changeover

Headset on before start							
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.						
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)							
Exit Deimos Software (x)							
POWER CHANGEOVER							
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton						
Restart Deimos Software							
System running again						at time	

Flight:

B292

KEY

- Duff Data
- Minor Problems
- OK
- Not Fitted
- Fitted, Not Operated

Thermometers

- Cabin Temperature:
- Heimann:
- Deiced Temp:
- Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

- FWVS:
- General Eastern:
- Johnson Williams:
- Nevezorov:
- Total Water Probe:

Cameras

- Downward Facing:
- Forward Facing:
- Rearward Facing:
- Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

- Cruciform GPS:
- GIN Applanix:
- INU Honeywell:
- Radar Altimeter:
- RVSM IAS:
- RVSM Static Pressure:
- XR5 GPS:

Report Created 26/06/2007
15:40:12

Misc Core

- AMTG:
- AVAPS:
- Cabin Pressure:
- Fax machine:
- Printer:
- S9 Static Pressure:
- Satcom C:
- Satcom H:
- Turb Centre-Static:
- Turb Left Right:
- Turb Up-Down:
- Turb Horizontal Chk:
- Turb Vertical Chk:
- Weather Radar:
- DLUs:**
- DLU AERACK:
- DLU BBR Lower:
- DLU BBR Upper:
- DLU Core Chem:
- DLU Core Consoles:
- DLU Port Aft:
- DLU Port Fwd:
- DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

- Lower:**
- BBR (clear) Lower:
- BBR (IR) Lower:
- BBR (red) Lower:
- Upper:**
- BBR (clear) Upper:
- BBR (IR) Upper:
- BBR (red) Upper:
- ARIES:
- DEIMOS:
- IR Camera:
- JNO2 Lower:
- JNO2 Upper:
- JO1D Lower:
- JO1D Upper:
- MARSS:
- SHIMS Lower:
- SHIMS Upper:
- SWS:
- TAFTS:

Last Updated:

Cloud Probes

- 2DC:
- 2DP:
- FFSSP:
- PCASP:
- ADA:
- CCN:
- CDP:
- CIP 100:
- CIP 25:
- CPI:
- CVI:
- SID1:
- SID2:
- Aerosol**
- CPC 3025A:
- Filters 47mm:
- Filters 90mm:
- Neph - Dry:
- Neph - Wet:
- PSAP:
- AMS:
- CPC 3025 (AMS):
- INC:
- VACC:
- CPC 3010A (CVI):

08/05/2007 15:56:35

Chemistry

- CO Aerolaser 5002:
- NOx TE42C:
- Ozone TE49C:
- Ozone TE49:
- SO2 TE43C:
- TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
- TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
- FAGE:
- Formaldehyde:
- NOxy:
- ORAC:
- PAN:
- PERCA:
- Peroxide:
- PTRMS:
- TDLAS (1C):
- WAS Bags:
- WAS Bottles:
- Misc Non-Core**
- CASI/ATM:
- LIDAR:
- LTI:
- SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B292

Date: 4 May 2007

Instruments

1. Satcom phone not working
2. Satcom messages being sent and received on the ground, none incoming - *only part of flight*
3. Downward facing camera cycling contrast control
4. TWC overheated for 20mins at low level fine after P4 *# of (4094) heaters dropped*
5. Inability of some hiemann cal progs to initialise
6. *2 sondes - 1 w/ launch detect / no launch detect.*
7. *MARS CH 16.*
- 8.

Aircraft

Nil

Satcom-H Calls

Not working

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) $\frac{1}{4}$ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 04/05/07

Flight No: B292

Pre-Flighter: JT/BW/RP

Item	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
1	<input type="checkbox"/>	Hangar	Collect Dustbin, put on a/c	
<u>Aircraft Cabin</u>				
2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	
3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Aft CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
6	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
7	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Recording data	
8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
9	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	ERRORS HD 2 OF 8
10	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
11	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nezvorov	Checked and OFF	Ⓢ
12	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GPS	Checked	
13	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Align	
14	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
16	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	
17	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	FWVS	Set up	LOSS
18	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	
19	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked / Set	
20	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
21	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC	ON & Checked	NOT FITTED YET
22	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Balance checked	
23	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Navigate then back to Align	
24	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Hubs x 4	Checked ON	
25	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd Console	Miss. Sci Laptop CB made	& CB on Port Fwd SSP
26	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CNC	Butanol filled	
27	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CGPS	Set up	
28	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
	<input type="checkbox"/>			

External Checks overleaf →

Pre-Flighter's Log

<u>Item</u> <input type="checkbox"/> or <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
<u>External</u>			
29	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
30	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	<i>Same broken</i>
34	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
36	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Camera Windows	Cleaned	
37	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Heimann	Lens checked OK	
38	<input type="checkbox"/> TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
39	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> All other covers	Removed	
40	<input type="checkbox"/> Dustbin	Returned to hangar	
41	<input type="checkbox"/> Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
42	<input type="checkbox"/> Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>			
43	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		Signed <i>[Signature]</i>
44	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ICEX applied		
45	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Traps empty (weekly only)		<i>[Signature]</i>

Flight B292 16:05:25

Heading 181 deg Speed 329 knots Height 26.0kft Press 359mb

Lat 25°30.0'N Long 92°0.0'W Wind 9 ms-1/ 276 deg

Temp -27.94C Dewpoint -50.49C

From 14:05:04 to now

CLIMB OUT OF HOUSTON.

Current values		
++++	STATIC PRESSURE	359.3 mb
++++	DEICED TRUE AIR TEMP	-27.95 deg C
++++	DEW POINT	-50.5 deg C

Flight B292 15:40:33

Heading 94 deg Speed 336 knots Height 26.0kft Press 359mb

Lat 27°36.0'N Long 92°6.0'W Wind 8 ms-1/ 276 deg

Temp -28.25C Dewpoint -47.0C

From 13:14:59 to now

*CLIMB OUT OF
NOVSTON*

Current values
PRESSURE HEIGHT 7930.51 m
++++ CNC COUNTS 46.9 p cm-3

● All
○

Flight B292 18:34:39

Heading 3 deg Speed 216 knots Height 0.1kft Press 1008mb

Lat 25°54.0'N Long 92°0.0'W Wind 13 ms-1/ 159 deg

Temp 25.08C Dewpoint 24.62C

From 14:59:19 to now

	Current values			
	PRESSURE HEIGHT	37.91	m	⊙ All
++++	CNC COUNTS	1680	p cm-3	⊂

Flight B292 15:32:06

Heading 95 deg Speed 337 knots Height 24.0kft Press 392mb

Lat 27°36.0'N Long 93°6.0'W Wind 6 ms-1/ 283 deg

Temp -23.42C Dewpoint -44.7C

From 13:03:06 to now

Climb to 26 kft

Current values			
	PRESSURE HEIGHT	7322.07	m
++++	OZONE MIXING RATIO	56.46	ppb
++++	CO MIXING RATIO	165.23	ppb

Flight B292 15:33:47

Heading 95 deg Speed 337 knots Height 24.0kft Press 392mb

Lat 27°36.0'N Long 92°54.0'W Wind 6 ms-1/ 285 deg

Temp -23.48C Dewpoint -47.07C

From 13:03:06 to now

Handwritten: clear to 26kft

Current values			
++++	PRESSURE HEIGHT	7321.3	m
++++	OZONE MIXING RATIO	56.08	ppb
++++	CO MIXING RATIO	169.88	ppb

Flight B292 18:35:53

Heading 4 deg Speed 216 knots Height 0.1kft Press 1008mb

Lat 26°0.0'N Long 91°54.0'W Wind 14 ms-1/ 161 deg

Temp 25.15C Dewpoint 24.51C

From 13:03:06 to now

Current values			
++++	PRESSURE HEIGHT	40.18	m
++++	OZONE MIXING RATIO	18.27	ppb
++++	CO MIXING RATIO	131.18	ppb

Flight B292 15:56:57

Heading 183 deg Speed 324 knots Height 26.0kft Press 359mb

Lat 26°12.0'N Long 92°0.0'W Wind 11 ms-1/ 270 deg

Temp -27.7C Dewpoint -50.17C

From 14:59:19 to now

*CLIMB OUT
OF
HOUSTON*

	Current values			
	PRESSURE HEIGHT	7933.33	m	⊙ All
++++	NEPH BLUE SP	2.77	m-1	⊂
++++	NEPH GREEN SP	0.25	m-1	⊂
++++	NEPH RED SP	-0.14	m-1	⊂

Flight B292 18:34:14

Heading 2 deg Speed 215 knots Height 0.1kft Press 1008mb

Lat 25°54.0'N Long 92°0.0'W Wind 12 ms-1/ 160 deg

Temp 25.03C Dewpoint 24.7C

From 14:59:19 to now

	Current values			
	PRESSURE HEIGHT	36.58	m	● All
++++	NEPH BLUE SP	107	m-1	○
++++	NEPH GREEN SP	111	m-1	○
++++	NEPH RED SP	123.01	m-1	○

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B292:

Log	Reason
Core Chemistry	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
FWVS	No log is taken for this FWVS
AMS	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	31 Aug 2007	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x Upward Facing Cameras
3 x Downward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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